

Cluster versus Individual Randomization in Prehospital, Emergency and Critical Care Trials: Protocol for a Meta-Epidemiological Study

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Introduction

Randomized clinical trials are the gold standard for evaluating the efficacy of medical interventions, as they minimize confounding and bias.¹ However, the level of randomization can significantly influence the outcomes and their interpretation.²⁻⁷ Two level-based approaches to randomization are individual randomization and cluster randomization. In individually randomized trials, participants are randomly assigned to different interventions at an individual level. In contrast, cluster-randomized trials allocate groups (e.g., hospitals, medical teams, or communities) rather than individuals, which introduces additional methodological challenges.^{2,7}

One major concern in cluster-randomized trials is the risk of selection bias due to lack of allocation concealment. Allocation concealment at a cluster-level is common in cluster-randomized trials, however true allocation concealment for the individual patient, who is not the initial patient in a cluster, is only possible if the intervention is double-blinded, which is rarely the case.⁶ The absence of strict allocation concealment can lead to exaggerated treatment effects, especially in open-label trials, where knowledge of the intervention may influence enrollment decisions, whether deliberately or unintentionally.^{7,8}

Systematic differences in effect estimates between cluster-randomized and individually randomized trials have been found.³ However, the extent to which such deviations are present, and whether they come with a risk of bias specifically in prehospital, emergency and critical care interventional trials remains unclear. Given the acute nature of these fields, selection bias could be amplified, as trial inclusion is often time-sensitive.

Objectives and hypotheses

The objective of this study is to assess the degree of deviations in effect estimates between cluster-randomized and individually randomized trials in prehospital, emergency, and critical care. The aim is to quantify whether these deviations are systematic, indicating potential biases.

We hypothesize that cluster-randomized trials will yield more extreme results than individually randomized trials, potentially due to allocation concealment-related selection bias.

Methods

This protocol outlines a meta-epidemiological study conducted as a systematic review with meta-epidemiological analyses to assess differences in effect estimates between cluster-randomized and individually randomized clinical trials in meta-analyses of interventions in critical, emergency and prehospital care. The study will adhere to the current pre-published protocol and follow proposed guidelines for conducting and reporting meta-epidemiological methodology research, including the

adapted Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA) statement and checklist.⁹ The protocol will be published on Zenodo.org (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15348609>) prior to literature screening.

Criteria for selection of meta-analyses

Types of studies

We will include meta-analyses that present a pooled intervention analysis including at least one cluster-randomized and one individually randomized clinical trial, which were published in the last decade; i.e., from January 1, 2015, to present day. If a meta-analysis has been updated, we will only include the most recent version. No language restrictions will be applied upfront.

Types of participants

Meta-analyses on interventions for acutely ill patients in prehospital emergency care, in-hospital emergency care, or critical care settings will be included. This includes, but is not limited to, patients under the care of prehospital emergency medical services or those admitted to the emergency department, coronary care unit, intermediate care unit, intensive care unit, or similar high-dependency hospital unit. Meta-analyses focussing solely on perioperative care interventions or interventions related to endovascular procedures will be excluded. However, any meta-analysis with overall inclusion criteria and a majority of included trials and participants complying with the target populations will be eligible for inclusion. No age restrictions will be applied, except that meta-analyses exclusively including neonates (infants during the first 28 days after birth) will be excluded.

Types of interventions

Meta-analyses on all randomized interventions either performed or authorized by prehospital emergency medical services, emergency physicians, intensivists, or other related in-hospital physicians will be eligible. Only interventions applied prior to or during hospital admission will be included, meaning that meta-analyses on post-discharge interventions in areas such as follow-up and rehabilitation, will not be included.¹⁰ Meta-analyses will be included regardless of the type of control group intervention. That is, we will include both active and inactive control interventions, including standard of care or placebo.

Types of outcome measures

The primary outcome will be mortality at the longest reported follow-up (dichotomous). The compiled secondary outcome (continuous or ordinal) will include any days-alive-type outcome,¹¹ such as days alive without life support, days alive and out of hospital, or days alive without coma or delirium, as

well as any length-of-stay-type outcome, e.g., ICU length of stay or hospital length of stay. If a meta-analysis includes multiple eligible outcomes for the compiled secondary outcome, the outcome reported for both cluster-randomized and individually randomized trials, with the largest number of participants included, will be selected.

Only data reported in the meta-analyses will be used by default. Data will not be systematically obtained from source trials; however, trial publications may be reviewed to clarify discrepancies. Meta-analyses not reporting on either the primary outcome or a relevant outcome for the compiled secondary outcome, will not be included in the quantitative analyses.

Search Strategy

Systematic reviews with meta-analysis fulfilling the criteria above will be identified through literature searching with systematic and sensitive search strategies as supplied in Appendix 1. We will search Pubmed/MEDLINE and EMBASE.

Selection of studies

Search results will systematically be screened independently and in duplicate by research group members SL and PLP, conducted in two separate steps as an initial title and abstract screening followed by obtainment of full texts of potentially relevant studies and full text screening of these. Any disagreement will be solved in consensus, or by consulting with senior researcher OLS. Search duplicates will be identified using the unique digital object identifiers (DOIs), as obtained through PubMed/MEDLINE and EMBASE, and removed prior to screening. Selection of results will be conducted using the web-based collaboration software platform, Covidence (www.covidence.org). Flow of the literature screening, including study in- and exclusion, will be visualised in a PRISMA flow diagram.¹²

Data extraction

Data will be extracted independently and in duplicate by research group members SL and PLP, using a standardized data collection form in Excel, which will be specifically designed. We will extract mortality at longest reported time-point as numbers and events in intervention and control groups from the included meta-analyses, and continuous outcomes as means with standard deviations. Data will be obtained from the published meta-analyses; original trial publications will only be assessed in the case of discrepancies. Only data from randomized trials, either cluster-randomized or individually randomized, will be included. Quasi-randomized trials will not be included. Data from multi-arm trials will be handled as in the included meta-analysis, i.e., selected or pooled.

Data synthesis

Clinical trials from each included meta-analysis will be grouped according to cluster randomization or individual randomization. We will use a multi-level hierarchical regression model where the third level is the meta-analyses and the second is the specific trials included in the meta-analyses, to test the group difference between cluster-randomized and individually randomized trials across the meta-analyses. We will report differences in effect sizes with 95% confidence intervals. Differences will be visualized in forest plots. Effect sizes for the primary, binary mortality-outcome will be calculated as $\ln(\text{odds ratios})$,^{13,14} and for the ordinal or continuous secondary outcome as Hedges' *g*-standardized mean differences.¹⁵ To visualize any systematic differences between cluster-randomized and individually randomized trials, the overall effect sizes from each meta-analysis will be compared using Bland-Altman plots. If a trial is represented in more than one meta-analysis for the primary or the secondary outcome, all trials from these meta-analyses will be compiled to a single estimate for the given outcome, ensuring that each trial is only represented once. We will estimate the $\ln(\text{odds ratios})$ by the numbers in the two-by-two tables reported in the meta-analyses to the extent possible. All analyses were conducted using STATA statistical software, release 18 (Stata Nordic, Stockholm, Sweden).

Risk of bias and quality of evidence

No risk of bias assessments of individual trials or grading of the overall evidence will be conducted, as the aim of the study is a meta-epidemiological assessment of overall deviations between methodological trial designs and not to quantify effect estimates of specific interventions to guide clinical practice.

Funding

The project received no specific funding and is conducted using departmental funding only.

Conflicts of interests

Research group members TLK and OLS are clinical trialists, involved in several individually randomized clinical trials in the field,¹⁶⁻¹⁹ as well as co-authors on conducted meta-analyses.²⁰⁻²² All other members of the research group report no conflicts of interest.

Ethics and dissemination

Since only data from published literature will be included, no patients are involved and consequently, no ethics approval is needed. Results of this meta-epidemiological study will be submitted for publication in a relevant peer-reviewed journal, preferably open-access.

Conclusion and perspectives

This meta-epidemiological study aims to quantify deviations in effect estimates between cluster-randomized and individually randomized trials in prehospital, emergency, and critical care settings. By determining whether these deviations are systematic and indicative of bias, we seek to enhance the reliability and interpretation of cluster-randomized clinical trials in systematic reviews and meta-analyses within acute settings. This could have significant implications for the methodological rigor, credibility, and future handling of cluster- versus individually randomized trials in meta-analytical research.

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Appendix 1 – Search Strategies

Search strategy for PubMed

Search Search Details

- 7 ("Critical Care"[MeSH Terms] OR "Intensive Care Units"[MeSH Terms] OR "Multiple Trauma"[MeSH Terms] OR "brain injuries, traumatic"[MeSH Terms] OR "Heart Arrest"[MeSH Terms] OR "Emergency Medical Services"[MeSH Terms] OR "Emergency Treatment"[MeSH Terms] OR "Critical Illness"[MeSH Terms] OR "intensive care*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Critical Care"[Title/Abstract] OR "critical ill*"[Title/Abstract] OR "critically ill*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency medical service*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency medical technician*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency treatment*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency medicine"[Title/Abstract] OR "ambulance*"[Title/Abstract] OR "first aid*"[Title/Abstract] OR "military medicine"[Title/Abstract] OR "prehospital*"[Title/Abstract] OR "pre hospital*"[Title/Abstract] OR "paramedic*"[Title/Abstract] OR "out of hospital*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency service*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency technician*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency practitioner*"[Title/Abstract] OR "first responder*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency rescue*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency resusc*"[Title/Abstract] OR "advanced life support*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency care practitioner*"[Title/Abstract] OR "traumatic brain injur*"[Title/Abstract] OR "multi* trauma*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Heart Arrest"[Title/Abstract] OR "cardiac arrest"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency health service*"[Title/Abstract]) AND (("Meta-Analysis as Topic"[MeSH Terms:noexp] OR "Meta-Analysis"[Publication Type:noexp] OR "meta analy*"[Text Word] OR "metanaly*"[Text Word]) AND ("random* trial*"[Title/Abstract] OR "random* stud*"[Title/Abstract] OR "RCT"[Title/Abstract] OR "random* controlled"[Title/Abstract] OR "random* clinical*"[Title/Abstract])) AND 2015/01/01:3000/12/31[Date - Publication]
- 6 2015/01/01:3000/12/31[Date - Publication]
- 5 ("Critical Care"[MeSH Terms] OR "Intensive Care Units"[MeSH Terms] OR "Multiple Trauma"[MeSH Terms] OR "brain injuries, traumatic"[MeSH Terms] OR "Heart Arrest"[MeSH Terms] OR "Emergency Medical Services"[MeSH Terms] OR "Emergency Treatment"[MeSH Terms] OR "Critical Illness"[MeSH Terms] OR "intensive care*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Critical Care"[Title/Abstract] OR "critical ill*"[Title/Abstract] OR "critically ill*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency medical service*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency medical technician*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency treatment*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency medicine"[Title/Abstract] OR "ambulance*"[Title/Abstract] OR "first aid*"[Title/Abstract] OR "military medicine"[Title/Abstract] OR "prehospital*"[Title/Abstract] OR "pre hospital*"[Title/Abstract] OR "paramedic*"[Title/Abstract] OR "out of hospital*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency service*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency technician*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency practitioner*"[Title/Abstract] OR "first responder*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency rescue*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency resusc*"[Title/Abstract] OR "advanced life support*"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency care practitioner*"[Title/Abstract] OR "traumatic brain injur*"[Title/Abstract] OR "multi* trauma*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Heart Arrest"[Title/Abstract] OR "cardiac arrest"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency health

- service*[Title/Abstract]) AND (("Meta-Analysis as Topic"[MeSH Terms:noexp] OR "Meta-Analysis"[Publication Type:noexp] OR "meta analy*[Text Word] OR "metanaly*[Text Word]) AND ("random* trial*[Title/Abstract] OR "random* stud*[Title/Abstract] OR "RCT"[Title/Abstract] OR "random* controlled"[Title/Abstract] OR "random* clinical*[Title/Abstract]))
- 4 ("Meta-Analysis as Topic"[MeSH Terms:noexp] OR "Meta-Analysis"[Publication Type:noexp] OR "meta analy*[Text Word] OR "metanaly*[Text Word]) AND ("random* trial*[Title/Abstract] OR "random* stud*[Title/Abstract] OR "RCT"[Title/Abstract] OR "random* controlled"[Title/Abstract] OR "random* clinical*[Title/Abstract])
 - 3 "random* trial*[Title/Abstract] OR "random* stud*[Title/Abstract] OR "RCT"[Title/Abstract] OR "random* controlled"[Title/Abstract] OR "random* clinical*[Title/Abstract]
 - 2 "Meta-Analysis as Topic"[MeSH Terms:noexp] OR "Meta-Analysis"[Publication Type:noexp] OR "meta analy*[Text Word] OR "metanaly*[Text Word]
 - 1 "Critical Care"[MeSH Terms] OR "Intensive Care Units"[MeSH Terms] OR "Multiple Trauma"[MeSH Terms] OR "brain injuries, traumatic"[MeSH Terms] OR "Heart Arrest"[MeSH Terms] OR "Emergency Medical Services"[MeSH Terms] OR "Emergency Treatment"[MeSH Terms] OR "Critical Illness"[MeSH Terms] OR "intensive care*[Title/Abstract] OR "Critical Care"[Title/Abstract] OR "critical ill*[Title/Abstract] OR "critically ill*[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency medical service*[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency medical technician*[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency treatment*[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency medicine"[Title/Abstract] OR "ambulance*[Title/Abstract] OR "first aid*[Title/Abstract] OR "military medicine"[Title/Abstract] OR "prehospital*[Title/Abstract] OR "pre hospital*[Title/Abstract] OR "paramedic*[Title/Abstract] OR "out of hospital*[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency service*[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency technician*[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency practitioner*[Title/Abstract] OR "first responder*[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency rescue*[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency resusc*[Title/Abstract] OR "advanced life support*[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency care practitioner*[Title/Abstract] OR "traumatic brain injur*[Title/Abstract] OR "multi* trauma*[Title/Abstract] OR "Heart Arrest"[Title/Abstract] OR "cardiac arrest"[Title/Abstract] OR "emergency health service*[Title/Abstract]

Search strategy for Embase.com

No.	Query
#14	#12 NOT #13
#13	'conference abstract'/it
#12	#10 AND #11
#11	[2015-2025]/py
#10	#4 AND #9
#9	#7 AND #8
#8	'random* trial*':ti,ab,kw OR 'random* stud*':ti,ab,kw OR 'rct':ti,ab,kw OR 'random* controlled':ti,ab,kw OR 'random* clinical*':ti,ab,kw
#7	#5 OR #6
#6	'meta analy*':ti,ab,kw OR metaanaly*':ti,ab,kw
#5	'meta analysis'/de OR 'meta analysis (topic)'/de
#4	#1 OR #2 OR #3
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#2	'cardiac arrest':ti,ab,kw 'intensive care'/exp OR 'intensive care unit'/exp OR 'multiple trauma'/exp OR 'traumatic brain injury'/exp OR 'heart arrest'/exp OR 'emergency health service'/exp OR 'emergency treatment'/exp OR 'critical illness'/exp OR 'patient transport'/exp
#1	